

The SHAPES Smart Mirror Approach for Independent Living, Healthy and Active Ageing

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Abstract: The benefits that technology can bring about in terms of health and support for independent living are in many cases not enough to break the barriers that prevent older adults from accepting and embracing technology. This work proposes a mirror-based platform equipped with a set of digital solutions whose main focus is to overcome older adults' reluctance to use technology at home and wearable devices on the move. The system has been experimentally validated, using a real setup aimed at two different purposes: support independent living for older individuals with neurodegenerative diseases and promote physical and rehabilitation activities at home. Results demonstrate the feasibility of such solution, not only in terms of usability, performance and accuracy but also in terms of privacy, data ownership and cost. It can be concluded that the SHAPES smart mirror has the potential to contribute as a technological breakthrough to overcome the barriers that prevent older adults from engaging in the use of assisted technologies.

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1. Introduction

The ageing of the world's population is a fact [1] with many implications that modern society has to currently face. Based on population pyramid forecasts and the increase in life expectancy or global average age [2,3], in a few years, the world's population will have more people over 65 than ever before. Based on these forecasts, the need to cover the different needs associated to ageing poses important challenges [4]. It is therefore necessary to identify and provide technological support to the aspects that are key to ageing with a high quality of life (QoL). It is also necessary to raise awareness about the facts that determine a healthy aging process [5].

Loneliness is one of the major problems faced by older adults. For instance, in Spain there are more than two million people over 65 living alone [6]. Besides loneliness, sedentary lifestyle is also a major health hazard, specially as people age. Avoiding a sedentary lifestyle, maintaining adequate physical and mental activity and a balanced diet are crucial for coping with age-related deterioration [7]. Similarly, health management and proper medication [8] together with good rest [9] have been identified as factors for a healthy ageing with high QoL.

Over the last decade, the Internet of Things (IoT) [10] and more specifically, the Ambient Assisted Living (AAL) [11] field has witnessed different technological innovations aimed at providing safe and interconnected environments intended to support independent living as long as possible. Smart homes [12], active ageing platforms [13] and smart devices [14] aim to address the different challenges of healthy ageing. However, while developers focus their design on older adults, there are numerous barriers overlooked leading to a lack of engagement [15]. According to [16], there is a list of factors that affect the attitude and intention to use technologies supporting independent living. These personal and device-related factors comprise use user expectancy, biophysical aging restrictions, anxiety, prior required knowledge, intrinsic motivation, personality, and privacy concerns. In this sense, some important aspects should be considered, specially when designing interfaces for older adults [15]:

- **Physical condition:** It is common for older adults to suffer physical impairments, so in the design of the interaction, impaired eyesight, haptic deterioration and reduced hearing has to be considered.
- **Computer literacy:** Older adults, in their majority, are unfamiliar with technology, so interaction with the interface and even with the use of the certain menus, buttons or other graphical interface user elements can be challenging. They have also a limited understanding of the processes and very frequently find that that the interface controls are non-intuitive.
- **Cognitive condition** Older adults also present different cognitive impairments, such as the reduction of the attentional control, visuospatial awareness and working memory. For this reason, the development of very intuitive interfaces is necessary to increase its usability for older adults.

To overlook such aspects is the main reason why older adults are reluctant to use technological assistance. It has been recently discovered [16] that, despite the benefits that the use of such technology innovations can bring to older adult's health, this cannot work alone as a motivator to overcome such as limiting factors. For this reason, special efforts have to be addressed to minimize the most common barriers found by older adults. In this sense, there are guidelines and standards specifically devoted to address such limitations [15]:

- **Interface and control design:** There are useful standards to comply with that state text size, color, and font, use of intuitive control elements, having constant feedback on what is being done and having contextual help. These are the basis for interface design.
- **Input controls:** Devices with touch screen are more intuitive for this age group, however, if there are physical limitations, voice commands are very convenient to execute different events, or even as text input. Another option is gaze-tracking devices, although this form of interaction is recommended primarily as an option for users with severe motor impairment. Finally, using TV-like interfaces or using devices similar to a TV remote control makes them comfortable when using applications that incorporate them.
- **Natural language:** Older users are often confused by long messages with many options. If we offer the user too many choices they may feel confused and overwhelmed in making the right choice. On the other hand, using simple descriptive language makes the interface more intuitive for them.
- **Cognitive Evaluation:** The employment of digital assistance and smart devices in older adults allows caregivers to monitor and support their cognitive state, facilitating the early detection of cognitive decline.

The SHAPES project ¹ (Smart & Healthy Ageing through People Engaging in Supportive Systems) is an European-funded Innovation Action intended to promote

¹ <https://shapes2020.eu/>

long-term healthy and active ageing as well as to maintain a high-quality standard of life. In order to do so, SHAPES provides a set of digital solutions, deployed on EU-standardised open platform, supporting the factors that determine a healthy and active ageing. The validation of both the open platform and the digital solutions have been devised through a pilot campaign, organised in seven different themes. This paper presents an innovative platform evoking the idea of a magic mirror that will be tested in two of the pilot themes proposed in SHAPES², as known: Pilot Theme 5, concerning care for older individuals with neurodegenerative diseases, and Pilot Theme 6, which is focused on providing physical rehabilitation at home.

Mirrors have fascinated humans since their appearance, and it is no wonder that fiction is full of stories in which mirrors do much more than reflect, for example, predicting the future or revealing unconsciousness. Not only are mirrors appealing for fiction, but they have also been extensively studied in psychology. Mirrors, and more specifically their reflection, help us build our sense of self [17]. The SHAPES smart mirror approach is inspired by the human fascination for mirrors and the role they can play in enabling self-awareness by envisioning a future in which a smart mirror and a virtual assistant will guide individuals towards improved self-awareness and self-management of health.

This paper presents the mirror-based platform, devoted to support the execution and communication of digital solutions for independent living, healthy and active ageing. The smart mirror idea, by itself, is not disruptive as it can be observed from the list in Table 3. This table summarizes the most relevant contributions, to the date, along with the different characteristics that can be used to support active ageing.

Nonetheless, the novelty of this work lays on the combination of an attractive piece of hardware, as it is the SHAPES smart mirror, and a set digital solutions that put older adults in the centre of the design. This results in an innovative platform whose interfaces and interactions are natural and have been conceived aware of the limitations that prevent older adults from embracing technology.

This work describes the main features of the SHAPES smart mirror as well as the different digital solutions devised for Pilot Themes 5 and 6, providing support for independent living to people with neurodegenerative diseases and physical rehabilitation at home. The platform has been experimentally validated from the point of view of its usability and the performance of the hardware platform. Section 2 describes the different elements, both hardware and software, that comprise the proposed solution. SHAPES Pilot Themes 5 and 6 have been employed for validation purposes and section 3, therefore, provides the details of the different setups considered for validating the system and the different digital solutions. It also discusses the result obtained during the validation of the pilot setups. Finally, Section 4 presents the main conclusions drawn from this work.

2. Materials and Methods

The purpose of the platform presented here is twofold: 1) to support independent living for people with neurodegenerative diseases, and 2) to promote at-home physical activity and rehabilitation routines. To this end, a set of hardware and software systems have been devised, fit-for-purpose, revolving around the SHAPES smart mirror.

The first subsection describes the SHAPES smart mirror platform from the point of view of the hardware that comprises it, whereas the second subsection describes it in terms of the role it plays as a smart gateway. As one of the aims of this platform is to support independent living at home, it is essential to count on a home monitoring system. A sensor-based solution is therefore proposed, having the smart mirror platform as the smart gateway that performs data collection, pre-processing and storage, as well as sensor configuration. Finally, the last subsection describes the different software systems proposed to support the goals of independent living and at-home exercise. The

² <https://shapes2020.eu/about-shapes/pilots/>

Table 1: Intelligent platforms and mirrors based on active aging

Reference	Type	Field	Features
[18]	Smart mirror	Fitness and health	Kinect camera to capture the user's movements. The system generates an avatar of the user's body and a contour shape that indicates the correct exercise position. Interaction with the mirror is through gestures.
[19]	Smart mirror	General	A Raspberry Pi device with a camera and a microphone provide multimedia services while ensuring high-level security throughout the system. Facial recognition system for authentication and voice recognition for interaction. For traffic, news or weather information, Amazon Alexa Voice Service is used.
[20]	Smart mirror	General	A Raspberry Pi device with a camera, a microphone and a speaker offer a smart mirror solution for smart home. Voice recognition and facial recognition techniques for authentication and interaction. Touch interaction through an infrared frame. Automatic wake-up module through an infrared induction module.
[21]	Smart mirror	Healthcare	A Raspberry Pi device with a camera for facial recognition with a tool based on python, OpenCV and deep learning. Temperature, humidity, pressure, noise and light in the room is measured through a microcontroller with LoRa and Bluetooth wireless transceiver. Mood detection with Microsoft Azure Emotion API, Calendar with Python and CalendarLabs API, Weather with Yahoo Weather API and Location with Google Maps API.
[22]	Smart mirror	General	Smart mirror with virtual assistant to interact with the lighting in the house and provide different information using Alexa. This system is composed of a Raspberry Pi with web cam with microphone and speakers. Motion detection, and face recognition are other characteristics.
[23]	Smart mirror	General	Smart mirror as information panel with clock, date, weather and traffics, alarm clock and daily reminder using Todoist Application and holiday calendar. A Raspberry Pi is the basis of this system.
[24]	Smart mirror	General	Comprises a Raspberry Pi, a display module, a wireless transceiver module, a clock module, a Bluetooth module, a speech synthesis module and auxiliary function module. Information about temperature, weather, date, time, news and other information.
[25]	Smart mirror	Social network	Display with the results of the sentiment analysis using Twitter on Raspberry Pi.
[26]	Smart mirror	Health	This health fitness system has different sensors are used such as DHT11 room temperature sensor, ultrasonic sensor, PIR motion sensor, IR temperature body, a weight foot scale to obtain user data. A USB camera connected to the Raspberry Pi of the smart mirror allows for facial recognition. BIA (Bioelectrical Impedance Analysis) history, BMI (Body Mass Index) analysis, weight history and body temperature are some of the data shown on the display and in the Android Application.
[27]	Smart mirror	General	The functionalities offered are date and time, weather information, personalized news, user's mail, user's calendar music, facial recognition, speech recognition and text-to-speech. An Android application is responsible for mirror access through facial recognition using Microsoft Azure. The information can be obtained by using services such as Dark Sky, RSS of the newspaper Perú 21, Google Calendar and Gmail.

Table 1 –continued from previous page

Reference	Type	Field	Features
[28]	Smart mirror	Healthcare and psychology	User tracking with respect to the affective state recognition from facial expressions. Ambient light change that gives feedback on the user's emotional state.
[29]	Smart mirror	Home security	Smart Mirror using DHT 22 sensors and image processing techniques to detect human intrusion like Yolo and Haar cascade classifier of the OpenCV. A Raspberry Pi and a camera to provide the latest news, weather information with touch based control or mobile based control.
[30]	Smart mirror	Home automation	The proposed system has a Raspberry Pi with camera and microphone. An ESP8266 is in charge of the home control. Facial Recognition and Biometric Identification are other functionalities. All the information collected by the mirror can be accessed via web.
[31]	Smart mirror	Smart assistance and General	Through a Raspberry pi and a Camera, facial recognition is performed to load the daily activities that correspond to that identified person. Improvements such as voice control and other functionalities are proposed for the future.
[32]	Smart mirror	General	Project with a Raspberry pi a camera and microcontroller with different sensors like fingerprint sensor, distance sensor, motion sensor, RFID reader and some other components. Protocols such as MQTT and Node-Red are used for the processing and visualisation of sensor data.
[33]	Smart mirror	Health	The proposed smart mirror is composed of a Raspberry Pi, a camera and speakers and a wristband. User detection employs Actcast. The Fitbit APi and wristband are used to acquire the user's biometrical information.
[34]	Smart mirror	General	Raspberry Pi, 4K LCD Screen and RGDB camera on top. The functionalities of the proposed system are portrait log, gesture and speech UI, life rhythm visualisation, touch control module, automatic wake-up module, user registration using Open CV and authentication and emotion detection.
[35]	Smart mirror	Health	Raspberry Pi and web camera for a mirror with facial recognition, emotion recognition and healthcare functionalities. General information like weather, to-do list and clock are the other functionalities of this proposal system. BMI and health data in the mirror using Fitbit app.
[36]	Smart mirror	General	A Rapsberry Pi, microphone, speakers and proximity sensors are the main elements of this design. Interaction through sensors and voice. The different modules it contains are notice, newsfeed, update notification, weather, schedule, status, MQTT events.
[37]	Smart mirror	General	Raspberry Pi, microphone and speakers use ALEXA for voice interaction. The features of this design are date, time, weather, greetings and voice services.
[38]	Smart mirror	Emotional and psychology	A mirror composed of a camera, LED lamps, speakers, microphone and an IoT board. The purposes of this mirrors are the communication with user through a chat bot, estimation of long-term depression through facial recognition, evaluation of conversation mood & tone through speech recognition and behavior identification through pose recognition.
[39]	Smart mirror	General, home automation	A Raspberry Pi, a camera, a microphone and a speaker are included in this mirror. The functionalities offered are face recognition, home automation and voice activation and control subsystem using Amazon services and Alexa skills. It also offers the latest news, calendar, weather forecast, clock, calendar and updates.
[40]	Smart cabinet	Ambient assisted living	This smart cabinet consists of a smart mirror and a medication sensing platform. This solution is defined as Smart Home in a Box (SHIB). Using amazon services, it is intended that this cabinet works as a medication store for the elderly, providing interaction through voice commands.

SHAPES smart mirror platform works as the computing node in which such systems run, as well as a provider of a natural interface for users.

2.1. The SHAPES smart mirror hardware

The first version of the SHAPES smart mirror platform was designed fit-for-purpose. To this end, the first prototype was devised as shown in the SolidWork³ prototype depicted in Figure 1. This design integrates the following components:

- A 22 inches screen.
- A Raspberry Pi 4.
- A Logitech C925 webcam.
- 2 W speakers.
- An RFID module.
- A USB input plug.

Figure 1. Smart mirror SolidWork prototype

The Raspberry Pi 4 works as the computing node, equipped with 8 GiB of RAM memory. This computing node supports the execution of the different digital solutions provided for the two pilot themes under evaluation. There are some storage functionalities that might also be delegated to private clouds. Specific Debian packages have been compiled and made available for an easy deployment. Also, the automatic provisioning with Ansible has been implemented. These software implementations will be made available at the end of the SHAPES project.

³ <https://www.solidworks.com/>

Figure 2. Component deployment in the back of the smart mirror platform

2.2. The home monitoring system

The SHAPES smart mirror platform has been originally devised to support and extend independent living for older adults suffering neurodegenerative as well as to support at-home physical activity and rehabilitation routines. To this end, the knowledge obtained from monitoring the home environment and the behaviour of the older adults that live there is essential.

Human action recognition has been, for a long time, one of the major challenges faced by scientific community. Different strategies have been employed, affecting privacy in different ways, such as those based on video, audio and/or sensors. Video-based and deep learning techniques have experienced relevant advances in assisted living [41], mainly due to the richer information provided by cameras [42]. However, privacy expectations are high [41] in the home environment and although safety is preferred over privacy, the context where the camera is located does impact on the technology acceptance [43].

The concept of privacy is broad [44], as it encompasses different dimensions, such as physical privacy, psychological privacy, social privacy and informational privacy. A good balance between functionality and privacy concerns, as well as cost, is essential for a successful adoption of technological solutions [16]. Although cameras provide richer information about the context, such level of detail is not always needed. In such situations, the trade-off between privacy and functionality favours privacy over the second. This is the case here, and for this reason a solely-sensor-based approach is proposed for the home monitoring system. However, the use of sensors also comes with a price in terms of privacy as device interoperability has traditionally been addressed by using manufacturer's private cloud. It is therefore necessary to devise a mechanism to ensure device interoperability, specially among different vendors, avoiding the use of vendors' cloud. To this end, an architecture is proposed that has the SHAPES smart mirror at its core, to perform data collecting, processing and storage.

The use of different communication technologies is also an aspect to be considered as this has an impact mainly on interoperability and price. Table 2 compares the most common technologies used for smart home monitoring. Among them, mainly because of the sensor variety and cost, the ZigBee technology outstands as the most appropriate

one for our purpose of supporting independent living for older adults with neurodegenerative diseases. Moreover, it also guarantees a low cost and low energy consumption, with the possibility of using sensors from different manufacturers. Nonetheless, despite using the same communication technology, different manufacturers using ZigBee would still require their own hub or gateway to support their devices. Luckily, an open source project, known as ZigBee2MQTT⁴, provides a way to interconnect devices of different manufacturers with ZigBee connectivity. It allows ZigBee devices to be controlled via MQTT⁵ through an event bridge. This requires a computing node to run the event bridge. This computing node needs a ZigBee interface. This type of interface is not very common, in fact, the Raspberry Pi 4 lacks of such communication interface. This limitation can be easily overcome thanks to devices such as the zig-ah-zig-ah! or zzh! device⁶. This is a small development board in the form of a USB stick, compatible with ZigBee2MQTT, which provides the ZigBee communication interface to our computing node, turning it into a gateway, therefore working as a protocol coordinator. The use of both elements results in a much more cost-effective option for connecting a wide range of devices. Figure 3 summarizes the proposed architecture.

Table 2: Communication technologies comparative

Feature	WiFi	Bluetooth	Z-Wave	ZigBee
Energy consumption	High	10 MW	1 MW	100 MW
Range	1000 m	10 m	30 m	100 m
Cost	Medio	Muy bajo	Alto	Bajo
Escalability	32	20	<6000	6000
Interoperability	WiFi Comptabile devices	Bluetooth compatible devcies	Diferent Manufacturers	Same manufacturer ⁷

Figure 3. ZigBee devices coordinated by a zzh!

⁴ <https://www.zigbee2mqtt.io/>

⁵ <https://mqtt.org/>

⁶ https://www.zigbee2mqtt.io/information/supported_adapters.html

Most of the state-of-the-art platforms for IoT are cloud-based solutions. The use of the cloud offers a simple way (although not the most efficient one) of addressing the heterogeneity (in terms of devices and networks) in IoT. Many inconveniences are, nevertheless, derived from implementing entirely-cloud-based solutions such as high latency, resource consumption, low fault tolerance, or unnecessary data transportation for services that support their responses on local information, without needing aggregated or historic data. Another major inconvenience of a cloud-based solution arises when the cloud is owned by the manufacturer, and control is lost over its processing. The proposed solution overcome these limitations by using the SHAPES smart mirror platform as a data hub where, after a pre-processing stage, decisions are made about locally storing or pushing the data to a private-cloud solution, after going through the appropriate mechanisms to ensure data privacy and security issues.

The implemented system is based on the use of a number of sensors, including: motion sensors, door and window sensors, and temperature and humidity sensors. The motion sensors use infrared technology to detect movement within a specific range. This sensor provides information such as where the person is within the home. The door and window sensor is based on magnetic contact technology. Basically, this sensor is considered as a home security sensor, but it is useful in the context of assisted environments because it provides information about the state in which a door or window is found or if it is opened in an unusual way (breakage).

Temperature and humidity sensors are used to monitor the thermal variation inside a home. This sensor provides information that can be very relevant to ensure the well-being of the older adult. Due to their age, older adults are less sensitive to detect changes in the ambient temperature and this can have an impact on their health, for example, resulting in dehydration.

This set of sensors provide enough information to supervise the person behaviour and well-being. This setup can be easily enhanced with other sensors, independently of the manufacturers, such as water overflow, vibration, light intensity, smoke, CO₂, or energy consumption, just to name a few. As long as ZigBee communication is supported, the use of zzh! guarantees an easy integration. Among the different manufacturers, the proposed system has been built using the Aqara and Mijia sensors provided by Xiaomi. The selected sensors will be deployed following the architecture depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Architecture of the monitoring system

The proposed architecture has been implemented using the ZigBee wireless communication protocol and the MQTT messaging protocol for transporting the data collected

and published by the sensors. A Telegraf client⁸ has been used as a subscriber to the topics created for the different rooms of the house where sensors are located. The data is stored in a temporal database, either locally or in the cloud, using for this purpose the InfluxDB database⁹. The integration of InfluxDB and Grafana¹⁰ is direct, so a visualisation solution is obtained in a simple and efficient way. The dashboard offers information that is easy to interpret for both the older adults and their caregivers.

The SHAPES smart mirror works as the hub or a gateway. Although initially, the smart mirror lacks of ZigBee communication support, the use of the zzh! coordinator enhances it with a ZigBee interface. The smart mirror will be therefore running the following services:

- ZigBee2MQTT
- Broker Mosquitto Eclipse
- MQTT client implemented in Python
- Telegraf
- InfluxDB
- Grafana

The ZigBee2MQTT system listens the values measured by the different sensors and publishes them in the corresponding topic. The publication consists of a message with the event structure provided by MQTT, organized by entities and attributes. In this case, the entities are the sensors used, while the attributes are the data emitted by the sensors themselves. These attributes vary depending on the sensor, although they commonly share the following attributes:

- **Time:** Data recording time.
- **Battery:** Remaining battery life of the device, measure in percentage (%).
- **Host:** Device that provides values to the database. In this case, the host is the smart mirror.
- **Link quality:** Signal strength or quality of received data actually received. It is a value from 0 to 255, with 255 being the best possible quality.
- **Topic:** Topic where the Telegraf agent has subscribed to collect the values published by the sensors.
- **Voltage:** Battery voltage measured in millivolts (mV).

Each sensor has a specific attribute in addition to these common attributes. Thus, the door and window sensor has the contact attribute which is a binary value indicating whether the door and/or window contact is open or closed. The motion sensor has the occupancy attribute, which is a binary value indicating whether the device detected occupancy in the room. The temperature and humidity sensor has the attributes of pressure, temperature and humidity, numeric values indicating the atmospheric pressure measured in hectopascals (hPa), temperature measured in degrees Celsius (°C) and humidity measured in percentage (%). The key to each of the attributes is the topic where the sensors publish the data they collect from the dwelling.

The use of Telegraf is proposed to collect, process and send the data metrics provided by the different sensors to a database. In the architecture proposed here, the Telegraf agent subscribes to the topic «zigbee2mqtt/smart-sensors/#», where the data collected by the sensors is published. InfluxDB has the structure of the event channel attributes. Finally, the Grafana data analysis platform is connected to the InfluxDB database to enable the visualization of the stored data. Grafana is configured to provide a dashboard with as many panels as there are rooms in the monitored home (living room, kitchen, bedroom and bathroom, for example). Each of these panels shows the collected values.

⁸ <https://docs.influxdata.com/telegraf/v1.19/>

⁹ <https://www.influxdata.com/>

¹⁰ <https://grafana.com/>

Different roles are identified in the management of this architecture, namely: the administrator, the home user and the family or caregiver user. The system administrator is in charge of ensuring the correct functioning of the system. The home user is the person monitored by the system. Finally, the family user or caregiver is the one who supervises the wellbeing of the monitored person. The administrator role has permissions to manage the services but does not have access to the data in the database. He/she will only have access to this data if the home user grants his/her consent. The home user can also grant partial permissions to access the data, allowing, for example, his or her family members to have access to all the data but the professional caregiver does not have access to the data generated in the toilet or the bedroom.

2.3. *The smart mirror applications*

The SHAPES smart mirror provides a unique platform in which different applications can be deployed and run offering valuable services to promote healthy and active ageing. Although the major goals of the SHAPE smart mirror platform presented here are to support independent living and to promote at-home physical activity, these objectives will be pursued by addressing three of the major risk factors determining older adults' health and well being as known: social isolation, falls and physical inactivity. The following subsections describe the different software solutions devised to address such challenges.

2.3.1. The Call Service

The COVID-19 outbreak has caused a major, and unprecedented, health crisis. Efforts have been addressed to provide urgent medical attention to those going through the disease. The population confinement has been one of the most effective means to avoid the spread of the disease. This has, however, contribute to worsen the isolation situation already suffered by many older adults that live alone. These part of the population are, on their majority, technological illiterate, meaning that both access and use of technology cannot be faced without assistance.

Communication technologies running on tablets, smart phones or computers have been designed with the general public in mind, overlooking the needs of a specific part of the population, such as older adults. Only a small portion of the older adults effectively use such communication tools.

The call service described here is therefore intended to address social isolation, in general, but particularly that suffered under a pandemic context. The SHAPES smart mirror platform provides a perfect platform for video-conference purposes since it can handle both video and audio. Efforts have been therefore addressed to provide a call service that put the focus on ensuring the acceptance and satisfaction of the older adult population. Following a co-designed approach, different participants and experts from the SHAPES project were involved thorough the different iterations of the design, implementation, and testing phases. This has ensured the usability, user acceptance and satisfaction of the resulting technology. The result is a video-call service built upon the Telegram network¹¹. This service offers an interface specifically designed to run on the smart-mirror platform in such a way that interaction is kept to a minimum. Although all functionalities of Telegram would be available, the focus has been made in providing a video-call service.

Users need their own telephone number, at least at the beginning of the configuration, as this will be the number associated when creating an account on the Telegram network. The contact(s) you wish to call also need to have an account on the same network. To simplify the call process, a system has been developed based on an RFID wristband which stores both personal information and contacts. The login or call process is initiated by approaching the wristband to the reader. If the system is not logged in,

¹¹ <https://telegram.org/z/>

e.g. in scenarios in which the smart mirror is shared among multiple users, the first step would be the login process. Otherwise, it would directly read the contacts or, if it is only one, it would start the video call. Figure 5 depicts the elements intervening in the video call.

Figure 5. Elements intervening in the Call Service

This is an intuitive systems that requires very little interaction from the user, other than approaching the band and, in some cases, select the contact they want to call. Figure 6 shows the interface displayed in the smart mirror, requesting the band to be scanned in order for the call to start. Additionally, the process of burning information in the smart band is also very simple and intuitive. Although the process can only be done once, this has been thought for a person, other than the user, to manage it as it requires some technological skills (scan QR code, for example). The device shown in Figure 7 has been designed to simplify the process. The QR code should be scanned with a smartphone. This opens a very simple interface, like the one depicted in Figure 8. When the smart band is placed in the labelled square and the information has been provided to the appropriate field, by pressing the *write* button the information will be written to the band.

Figure 6. The call service interface

Figure 7. The interface for the RFID writer device

Figure 8. Wristband RFID writer device

2.3.2. The Fall Detector

One of the major risks to be addressed, with the expected ageing of the population, is that of falls. Falls are one of the main causes of major injuries, psychological problems as side effects and even death in the most severe cases. To avoid or mitigate all these negative consequences, it is necessary to attend to the injured person as early as possible. The most vulnerable people are those who live alone and have no one to care for them. Technological solutions have already been created, such as push buttons that allow the user to notify a fall. These types of solutions, although useful, may not be fully effective in cases in which the victim is disorientated or may even lose consciousness. To meet this need, the smart mirror solution proposed here, provides an automatic fall detector system that, integrated with the call service, notifies the emergency contact when a possible fall is detected.

The fall detector operates as a service within the smart mirror platform. This service receives data from an external sensor connected via BLE (Bluetooth Low Energy). The sensor takes inertial readings from the person, thus being able to detect changes in movement such as those that would be caused by a fall. The sensor is placed at the user's waist, as this is the centre of gravity of the human body. By placing the sensor there, any movement that is likely to cause a loss of balance leading to a fall will be easily detected. The sensing device used here is the MetaMotionR sensor from the manufacturer Mbientlab¹², equipped with the following sensors:

- **Accelerometer:** It measures the acceleration in each of the sensor's axes. It is measured in $g(m/s^2)$.
- **Gyroscope:** It measures the angular velocity of each of the axes of the sensor, in $^\circ/s$.

Besides these parameters, the sensor provides, by means of an internal algorithm, the absolute orientation of the sensor. This information can be very meaningful for fall detection, as it could indicate whether a user is on the ground. This absolute orientation is also found in all three axes of the sensor, and Euler angles are used as a measure.

The sensor collects data from the user's movements and sends it back to smart mirror platform. The smart mirror collects this data, and from it, it will be able to recognise whether the user has experienced a fall. This process is based on a machine learning model, which has been previously trained with data from 17 different subjects.

¹² <https://mbientlab.com/>

An SVM (Support Vector Machines) model has been used as it is the one that has the best performance in this type of problems. These 17 subjects performed different activities in a controlled environment, classified into ADLs (Activities of Daily Living) and falls. From these activities, labelled data were generated and used to train the model to discriminate when a fall occurs. After testing the model, an accuracy of 100% can be reported in controlled environments. The model is currently being tested under real-world conditions in the Nursing Home SHAPES partner.

The smart mirror will therefore act as a gateway, collecting data and determining whether a fall has been detected or not. If a failure is detected, the smart mirror will notify the user's emergency contact via the call service (see Section 2.3.1). This enables prompt response to the fall, even in cases of disorientation or loss of consciousness of the victim. Because this solution uses BLE, it is intended to monitor a person in the same environment in which the mirror is placed, as BLE has a limited range of approximately 5 metres. It is also possible to use coverage extenders if necessary. The system's operation is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Fall Detector

2.3.3. The Physical Activity Monitor

According to the WHO [45] “at least 80% of all heart disease, stroke and diabetes and 40% of cancer could be prevented” by tackling the most common risk factors underlying the most prevalent chronic conditions, such as unhealthy diets, physical inactivity, hypertension or obesity.

Off-the-shelf devices and Apps can be found for physical activity and weight management such as those of Fitbit¹³, Apple¹⁴, Google Fit¹⁵ or Xiaomi Mi Band¹⁶. They all offer a range of functionalities for user engagement, monitoring, reminders for promoting a healthier lifestyle, etc. Most of these commercial solutions offer open APIs, so that third party applications can access the data they collect. So, efforts can be focused on what to do with the data rather than how to collect them. However, a recent study [46] concluded that there is little evidence that wearable devices could improve health outcomes in older adults, although they could improve motivation and physical activity. Current approaches rely on wearable devices as enablers of behavioural change and most studies to date focus on healthy individuals rather than on those already suffering from a chronic condition or multi-morbidity.

The solution proposed here, named Phyx.io, take this technology a step further, enhancing the facilitating capability of *smartbands* with the potential functionalities that

¹³ <https://www.fitbit.com>

¹⁴ <https://www.apple.com/es/watch/>

¹⁵ <https://www.google.com/fit/>

¹⁶ <https://www.mi.com/es/mi-smart-band-5/>

can be supported by the smart mirror platform. This combination enables more efficient interventions towards physical activities, which will eventually lead to better a health and well being.

Phyx.io is a platform which automatically manages and monitors many health-related parameters affecting older adults. This is carried out through the commercial Mi Band 4 smart band, providing information about the most relevant health parameters. The Phyx.io platform collect and process the following information:

- **Activities:** The activities that the user has carried out in a 24-hour period, among the following ones: asleep state, offline state, walking state and resting state.
- **Calories:** Calories burnt, based on the activity and intensity of the carried out activities.
- **Number of steps:** The number of steps taken by the user, automatically tracked.
- **Heart beat:** The system will automatically and repeatedly record the heart rate indicating the maximum value, the minimum value and the current value.
- **Sleep quality:** It considers two sleep states, as known: light sleep and deep sleep.

The Mi Band 4 smart band records these health parameters and stores them internally. This information is not sent to the Xiaomi cloud as privacy and data protection are major concerns of the smart mirror platform. The information is therefore retrieved through a Bluetooth connection between the Mi Band 4 and the smart mirror, as depicted in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Physical Activity Monitor

A service has been developed to establish a point-to-point connection between the Mi Band 4 smart band and the smart mirror. This service has been built on the Python library Pygattlib¹⁷. Once the information is retrieved from the smart band, it does not necessarily mean that this has to remain locally, in the smart mirror. It can be sent to a private cloud, from where the Phyx.io system can access it for displaying purposes. Phyx.io has a built-in dashboard, in which such health parameters can be explored, as shown in Figure 11.

¹⁷ <https://github.com/oscaracena/pygattlib>

Figure 11. Dashboard Physical Activity Monitor

Phyx.io does not only monitor physical activity parameters, but it also intervenes by making recommendations and by supervising the performance of physical-exercise routines intended to recover or maintain the physical shape.

Recommendations are made through the Mi Band 4 smart band. These can be intended to promote physical activity, either by encouraging to walk and achieve a step goal or by means of reminders of a scheduled physical-exercise routine. Recommendations can also be addressed to ensure the general well being, such as *drink water* recommendations on hot days or general reminders. These recommendations are configured by the caregiver or the therapist, in case of physical activity goals and routines.

Phyx.io supervises the performance of physical-exercise routines prescribed by a therapist. The purpose of such session can either be the recovery from an injury or just to stay physically active. The recovery routines are categorised in orofacial rehabilitation exercises and the rest-of-the-body exercises. For the latest, a kiosk version as the one depicted in Figure 12 has been devised. Equipped with a depth camera, Phyx.io supervises and corrects the performance of the different exercises comprising a routine. The system is an advanced version of the one described in [47].

Figure 12. Phyx.io rehabilitation kiosk

For the orofacial rehabilitation exercises we have developed a lightweight computer vision-based system that employs three Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) to detect faces,

facial keypoints and the considered facial gestures, respectively. The deployment of these DNNs is optimized for mobile/IoT platforms using MediaPipe and TensorFlow Lite for the inference. First, the user's face detection is performed by BlazeFace [48]. This DNN is related in structure to MobileNetV1/V2 [49,50] and the Single Shot Multibox Detector (SSD) framework [51], and is aimed at effective GPU utilization in mobile/IoT devices. Its output is used to initialize another DNN [52], which allows inferring a dense 3D mesh representation of the user's face. Thus, based on the localized facial keypoints we rotate and rescale the facial images into normalised face patches in order to minimize the impact of facial image shape and appearance differences that could affect the subsequent gesture recognition stage.

In this setup we have considered the following 17 gestures for orofacial rehabilitation: *bite_lower_lip*, *bite_upper_lip*, *frown*, *kiss_left*, *kiss_right*, *kiss*, *neutral*, *open_mouth*, *press_lips*, *rise_eyebrows*, *show_teeth*, *smile_left*, *smile_right*, *smile*, *tongue_forward*, *tongue_left*, *tongue_right*. We have extracted normalised face patches from 19 people performing several repetitions of these gestures in uncontrolled 'in-the-wild' environments to train a DNN for image classification based on EfficientNet-lite0 [53]. This DNN is the most efficient version of the EfficientNet-lite mobile/IoT friendly image classification models. Its output is a 17-dimension vector of floating-point numbers that go from 0 to 1. This trained model serves as the reference guide for users. Thus, if the user performs one gesture close to the learned reference, the output will be close to 1 for that gesture. This way the system can automatically evaluate how well the user is performing every gesture. Thresholds could be configured to determine whether a user performs sufficiently well the gestures in real time and to analyse the evolution through time. Figure 13 shows some examples of the recorded reference images.

Figure 13. Examples of reference orofacial gesture images.

The physical therapist or trainer play a key role, not only prescribing exercise routines but also supervision the evolution, especially under rehabilitation processes. To this end, Phyx.io offer a dashboard view with records over time. The idea is that, even if the Phyx.io system corrects wrong body-posture or accompany the user during the routine, experts can latter on access the information generated during the routine. This can help evaluating adherence to the prescribed routine, level of achievement (for example, based on the number of repetitions prescribed and actually performed), accuracy of the performed exercise measure against the baseline pattern, time, etc.

Finally, it has been demonstrated [54] that older adults receive less social support and have more fear of falling during physical activity. This can lead to a poor adherence to exercise programs to users living alone, both for the lack of social support or motivation or the fear of a falling going unnoticed.

To address the lack of social support, Phyx.io is enhanced with capabilities for a one-to-one communication with physical therapist, trainer, or a exercise colleague. The idea is that users perceive exercising with Phyx.io almost as though they were training in a gym with the expert or other users by their side. First sessions are prone to demand expert support, or the need to feel accompanied, specially to address doubts. The call service has been embedded in the Phyx.io interface in such a way that video calls can be initiated during the performance of an exercise, or in a scheduled manner. This is very useful not only for user adherence but also for experts to receive feedback from users.

The fear of falling is addressed here by the fall detection system presented in Section 2.3.2. Users wear the MetaMotionR sensor in their waist so that when a fall is detected by the system, a call is launched through the call service to the emergency contact.

2.3.4. The Voice Assistant

The conversational interface provided by voice-based digital assistants is more intuitive and easier to use than hand-keypad or touch based input interfaces [55]. A voice assistant, embedded in the SHAPES smart mirror, could therefore provide a natural-language based interaction. Nevertheless, privacy and security concerns [56] have been recently arisen with regard to the use of this technology by vulnerable users, such older adults.

Digital assistants such as Siri, Alexa, and Google Assistant based their strengths in the currently available processing power and the large amount of information these companies have been able to collect and process to train advanced machine learning models that deliver personalised services [57]. Nevertheless, the use of such technologies come with a *privacy trade-off*, similar than the one stated for the health recommender systems [58]. A work-around to this privacy trade-off is to provide our own voice assistant, similarly to the approach we have previously describe for the home and physical activity monitoring systems.

The proposed architecture is based on the use of a set of voice assistant services provided by the Rhasspy tool¹⁸. From all the services provided by Rhasspy (see Figure 14) the proposed solution just employs the speech to text transcription service, the intent recognition service, and the intent handling service. For speech recognition, a model for the Spanish language has been trained with DeepSpeech which is a speech recognition engine based on a trained model using machine learning techniques¹⁹.

18

19

Figure 14. Rhasspy

The proposed solution follows the steps depicted in Figure 15. The voice assistant provides an intuitive manner of accessing the video-call service, other than using the RFID wristband. In this sense, the following steps describe the workflow for launching a video call to a particular contact using the voice assistant:

Figure 15. Voice assistant workflow

1. The audio input that is received is transcribed with the trained Spanish model and the speech recognition service. In this case, the audio input is the phrase quoted by the caller and the name of the contact with whom he/she wants to make the call.
2. The intention is recognised with the intention recognition service and mapped against the intention to make a call.
3. The call service is launched via the intention handling service, by triggering the command that perform a call to the contact stated in the audio input.
4. The call service starts the call.

2.3.5. Calendar with reminders

Multi-morbidity is highly prevalent, reaching up to 90% of people over 65 [59]. This is, at the same time, very challenging because different professionals are involved in the treatment, medication is complex and involves polypharmacy with a high risk of drugs interfering with each other, or poor medication adherence. According to [60] polypharmacy is usually associated with poor adherence. Non-adherence, when unin-

tentional, may be due to forgetting or lack of reminders [61]. The work in [62] analyses the different applications found in the Apple App Store and the Google Play Store. The use of medication reminders were positively perceived by users. In this sense, different approaches can be found in the literature such as the work in [63] that proposes a system based on SMS reminders or the one in [64], in which a calendar with reminders is presented.

The use of reminders is not only relevant for medication adherence purposes, as it has also been demonstrated its positive impacts in adherence to physical activity interventions [65]. More specifically, the work in [66] proposed an approach based on the self-efficacy theory [67,68]. This approach consists in stating realistic and attainable goals combined with incentives in the shape of motivators or reminders. Following this approach, the SHAPES smart mirror platform provides support for reminders that complement the reminders also provided through the Phyx.io service, sent to the Mi Band 4 smart band.

This service displays events from two different calendars, one at the organisation level and one at the person level. The first category covers events that affect all users in the context of a multi-user smart mirror (i.e.: smart mirrors in a nursing home context). This might involve the event regarding an activity that takes place in the nursing home and to which all residents can attend. It also covers events that limit the use of the mirror, such as an appointment made for a video call, again in the context of a smart mirror with multiple users. It is important to note that all events registered in this calendar will be public, i.e., they will be displayed in the smart mirror interface without a previous authentication. Figure 16 shows an example of a shared event, as it is the case of a Yoga class taking place in a shared facility as it can be the gym of a nursing home.

Figure 16. Example of event recorded in the shared calendar

The second calendar handles events concerning a single subject, like those regarding medication reminders or relative's birthdays, for example. This calendar therefore requires the person to be authenticated with the RFID wristband mentioned during the description of the call service in Section 2.3.1. Figure 17 shows an example of a private event displayed in the smart mirror interface.

Figure 17. Example of event recorded in a private calendar

Apart from using the smart mirror interface, notifications can also be sent to the Mi Band 4 smart band, as described in Section 2.3.3. These notifications will cause the smart band vibration, along with a description of the event and the scheduled time. In order to receive such notifications, the user has to be within the range of the smart mirror or any of its replicas working as a signal extender, as depicted in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Reminders sent to the Mi Band 4 smart band

3. Results and discussion

The SHAPES project is undertaken a pan-European pilot campaign plan. This plan follows a human-centred co-creating and co-design approach meaning users and relevant stakeholders have been involved all over the different phases of development or throughout the entire technology life cycle. User-needs have been captured following such approach through the development of personas, user stories and use cases.

The SHAPES project has considered seven pilot themes and different pilot sites where such themes will be evaluated. Among them, this article concerns the pilot themes involving the Nursing Home “El Salvador” (SAL) partner, as known: Pilot Theme 5 “Caring for Older Individuals with Neurodegenerative Diseases” and Pilot Theme 6 “Physical Rehabilitation at Home”. Furthermore, pilot themes are also organised on the basis of a set of use cases, so that it can be guaranteed that the identified user needs receive proper attention.

Pilot Theme 5 “Caring for Older Individuals with Neurodegenerative Diseases” aims to improve the delivery of care, the management of health conditions and of activities of daily living, and the communication and social well-being of individuals with mild cognitive impairment. More specifically, SAL participates in the following use case: Use case 1, focused on providing a digital assistant for older people with mild cognitive impairment.

Pilot Theme 6 “Physical Rehabilitation at Home” is intended to provide the appropriate tools for a safe performance of physical activity and physical rehabilitation routines. This pilot theme will therefore address older individuals that need to recover from a certain accident or health issue (e.g.: stroke, fall, surgery, arthritis rheumatoid, osteoarthritis, etc.) but also those who, without having to recover from a specific problem, benefit from physical activity, preventing or improving frailty conditions.

Pilot Theme 6 considers four use cases although this work focuses on the three uses cases supported on the smart mirror platform, as known:

- Use case 2, Training of orofacial musculature: This use case will involve individuals whose orofacial musculature needs to be improve or maintained.
- Use case 3, Video-based rehabilitation tool: This use case will be intended to provide a support system for rehabilitation and physical activity exercises.
- Use case 4, Wearable Motion Monitoring Devices: This use case intendeds to provide additional information that can be used to assess the evolution of the rehabilitation process or just to assess and promote the physical condition of the individual wearing the proposed devices.

Different criteria (key performance indicators) have been established to evaluate the success of the different interventions devised for the considered pilot themes and use cases. This analysis is out of the scope of this article and will be part of the future

work. Nonetheless, this work focuses on evaluating the performance and success of the different technologies designed to support such intervention.

An experimental validation approach is proposed based on the different use cases designed for the considered pilot themes. The following subsections describe each of the considered use cases along with the validation carried out. Moreover, because the smart mirror platform is based on a Raspberry Pi 4 device and its computational resources are limited, the first subsection starts by assessing the performance of such platform when running the different systems.

3.1. The SHAPES smart mirror platform validation

Regarding the smart mirror platform, as an embedded system, its performance has been evaluated in terms of resource consumption and response time. This impact on the user experience and therefore on the user acceptance. A poor user experience will be perceived if software applications have a resource demand higher than the one provided by the Raspberry Pi 4.

The mirror is under development and it is expected to offer more services, so it is important to know what is the load it supports with the currently implemented services and what is the margin it can have for the integration of future services. In order to know the load supported by the mirror, it was monitored for a period of 24 hours to know if the use of resources is efficient or, on the contrary, the platform is being very strained. Throughout these 24 hours, the assessment service performed measurements every 10 minutes, calculating the CPU usage in that interval and the memory usage.

The results after the monitoring time were the following. In terms of the overall system, an average CPU usage of 3.56% was calculated, indicating that proper use is made of processing resources, with the possibility of increasing the work with future services. Memory usage averaged 32.2%, which is slightly more negative than CPU usage, but not critical at the moment. The temperature of the processor was also measured, as high temperatures can indicate very demanding loads or even malfunctioning of a component. During the monitoring period the temperature remained around 50°C, showing normal operation.

Additionally, besides monitoring the general system, individual processes were also monitored, so that in the event of finding any incidence in the overall system, it would be possible to study which processes were causing the performance problems. Among all the processes comprising the current SHAPES smart mirror solution, three stood out with the following data 3.

Table 3: Load of the three highly demanding processes

Service	Description	CPU	Memory
magic-mirror-2	Service in charge of managing the smart mirror interface	1.08%	8.38%
Miband-dc	Mi Band data collection service	1.34%	3.26%
Fall-detector	Service for data collection and fall detection by means of the MetaMotionR sensor	1.11%	8.79%

None of these services is characterised by intensive use of resources, only the magic-mirror-2 and fall-detector services stand out in terms of memory usage, although this does not seem to be a relevant problem for the time being.

The performance analysis confirms that the solution presented is quite efficient in the use of resources, offering an adequate user experience and with the capacity to extend the services that comprise the SHAPES smart mirror platform.

3.2. Use case 1: Digital assistant for older people with mild cognitive impairment

In order to validate the system performance under a realistic environment, a private home has been recruited and appropriately equipped with the hardware and software elements. The real home employed for this test have been equipped with the following hardware devices:

- Xiaomi Mijia sensors for door and windows, whose deployment can be observed in Figure 19
- Xiaomi Mijia movement sensors, whose deployment can be observed in Figure 20
- Xiaomi Aqara temperature and humidity sensors, whose deployment can be observed in Figure 21
- Raspberry Pi 4
- A Zig-ah-zig-ah! (zzh!) as observed in in Figure 22.

Figure 19. Door and window sensor

Figure 20. Movement sensor

Figure 21. Temperature sensor

Figure 22. zzh!

The selected sensors were deployed and configured to work in a private and real home, as the one depicted in Figure 23. This home has four rooms, as known: the living room, the bedroom, the kitchen, and the toilet.

Figure 23. Floor plan of the home

The living room was equipped with a movement sensor, a door and window sensor and the temperature and humidity sensor. Figure 24 depicts the different locations selected for such sensors.

Figure 24. Sensors deployed in the living room

The toilet was equipped with a movement sensor and a temperature and humidity sensor. Figure 25 shows the selected locations for such sensors.

Figure 25. Sensors deployed in the toilet

The kitchen was equipped with a movement sensor and a temperature and humidity sensor. Figure 26 shows the emplacement of the different sensors.

Figure 26. Sensors in the kitchen

The bedroom was equipped with movement sensors and door and window sensors. Figure 27 shows the location where such sensors were deployed.

Figure 27. Sensors in the bedroom

The smart mirror computing node, represented here by the Raspberry Pi 4, is equipped with the zzh! coordinator. This device enhances the smart mirror platform with ZigBee communication. This platform is installed in the living room covering the whole house.

The validation experiment has run for two months (March and April), during which sensor events were collected. This information captures the behaviour of both: the home environment and the person. 17456 events were collected, corresponding 11560 of them to the presence sensor, 1231 of them to the door and windows sensors and 4665 events to the temperature and humidity sensors. From the analysis of the information collected during this experiment, the following conclusions have been drawn, as known:

- The temperature of the dwelling has not suffered any important variation, always in the range of 20 °C and 26 °C and humidity between the 47 %H and 52 %H.
- The movement sensors provides information about where, in the dwelling, is the person located and therefore, carrying out activities. In between 9:00 a.m. and 2:00 p.m., no movement is detected in the dwelling. The person leaves the house for work. Then, between 23:00 p.m. and 7 a.m. only the bedroom area detects movement. The person is in the bedroom either sleeping (when no movement is detected) or preparing for it. During the afternoon, the main activity is located in the living room, apart from the periods during which the person visits the kitchen for meal preparation and eating.
- Regarding the door and window sensors, the information they provide is that doors are, most of the day, open, apart from the cooking or sleep time.

Figure 28. Dashboard for environment monitoring

The dashboard depicted in Figure 28 shows an example of real-time remote monitoring. This interface is thought for the caregiver to know about the environmental conditions of the dwelling or the state of a certain door or window. Furthermore, historic records can be retrieved for further analysis intended to identify behavioural patterns that help an early recognition of behavioural changes consistent with cognitive impairments.

Despite the simplicity of the information provided by the employed sensors, relevant information about the user behaviour can be drawn. Patterns such as waking up or lunch time, or the identification of the room where the person is expected to be depending on the time, are very useful. This knowledge supports an early identification of changes in behaviour which should be supervised in people suffering mild cognitive impairment. Once the user behavioural patterns have been learnt, the digital assistant can easily provide reminders, not only about medication but also about other daily life activities, such as having a meal or going to bed.

The digital assistant has been, so far, mainly focused on providing social interaction support. The validation of this system has therefore focused on its functionality to start a video call using natural language interaction. Using the smart mirror deployed in a real home setup, during a week different commands were launched and appropriately executed. Only one person, different than the ones used for training the model, has been issued commands. The video call service requires the person to be called to have the Telegram App installed in his/her device. To assist in this process, a video tutorial was prepared²⁰ guiding non-advanced users in the installation process. Video calls were launched in both ways, from the smart mirror to a contact and from the contact to a smart mirror. The digital assistant also provides functionalities for physical activity and medication adherence. In this sense, the use of a calendar with reminders have been implemented. For this functionality, the digital assistant is integrated with the Mi Band 4 smart band. Reminders are sent to both, the smart mirror and the smart band. Because such functionality is built upon the Bluetooth communication interface, so far, reminders can only be received in a home environment. Future implementations can also study the use of the smart phone as a bridge to deliver reminders to the smart band.

3.3. Use case 2: Training of orofacial musculature

Figure 13 shows that the performance of orofacial gestures could be quite subtle. In consequence, as it can be observed in the confusion matrix of the trained model shown in Figure 29, during the execution of these gestures there could be moments in which the appearance between different gestures could be similar. Therefore, users should try to perform gestures with the highest expressiveness possible to avoid this problem. Besides, the evaluation should consider the time frames with the obtained maximum intensities for each gesture, and ignore the gesture-to-gesture transitions.

²⁰ <https://youtu.be/auwTeeT3-zg>

Figure 29. Confusion matrix of the trained orofacial gesture detector.

3.4. Use case 3: Video-based rehabilitation tool

The success and acceptance of a certain software system is strongly determined by its usability. There are different ways to evaluate the system usability such as the System Usability Scale (SUS) [69] or the Post-Study System Usability Questionnaire (PSSUQ) [70]. Nonetheless, applications specifically designed for older adults, such as those thought to be run in ambient assisted living contexts, call for specific frameworks for usability assessment. This is the case of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health Usability Scale (ICF-US) [71]. This scale offers a way to evaluate digital solutions by focusing the designs on the end-user. This gets the feedback needed to find barriers and enablers in the mock-up phase through validated methodologies and procedures.

The International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health Usability Scale (ICF-US) [71] has two subscales. The ICF-US I enables a general usability assessment whereas the ICF-US II enables a more detailed assessment, evaluating each component of the design to detect elements that need to be modified (barriers) and good practices (facilitators) to be taken into account for further design of the solution [72–74]. Depending on the stage of development of the solution, one or both subscales may be chosen. Thus, ICF-US I will be applied for general usability evaluations, and ICF-US II will be used to evaluate mock-ups in early stages of development to find the weaknesses and strengths of the design. Phyx.io will be evaluated using the ICF-US II scale.

The ICF-US II is comprised of items that identify the components of a digital solution [71]. Each item can be evaluated as a barrier or enabler, with a maximum value of 3 and a minimum value of -3 or as not applicable (N/A) if it does not respond to the item. By doing so, it is possible to identify the components that need to be modified. The ICF-US II is specific to each digital solution although the structure is common and is divided into 3 parts:

1. Components of the application. In the first part we evaluate the components that comprise the digital solution.
2. Detailed usability. This part takes into account the different interaction functionalities as well as the user interface.

3. Overall system evaluation. This last part is composed of a general question about the contact with the system.

The Phyxio evaluation required an evaluator and an observer. The evaluator assesses the rating of each item through observation and interview. Therefore, the evaluator will base his/her answers on the observation of the user's interaction with the digital solution and on the interview to collect possible reasons why a component is a barrier or to clarify possible doubts about the user's interaction. On the other hand, the observer collects information considered necessary to ensure redundancy without taking any detail for granted.

The test has been initially prepared and completed by the professionals dedicated to older-adult healthcare. These professionals have a very important role in the Phyxio system, as they are responsible for the management of their patients within the platform. Assigning exercise routines, monitoring the state of health and physical activity or setting appointments or reminders are some of the tasks that this role can perform within the platform. Thus, the evaluation was conducted involving different professional profiles (physiotherapists, therapists) of the nursing home "El Salvador" (SAL). 10 participants were selected with an average age of 36.5, maximum 60 years and minimum 25 years. The assessment is carried out in one of the rooms of the physiotherapy team, in the SAL building.

The evaluator conducting the test introduces the Phyxio platform and provides the user with test credentials for authentication. Then, he/she proposes the healthcare professional to perform the following tasks to evaluate each item of the subscale. The tasks performed by each user are:

- Authenticate on the platform.
- Search something.
- Identify the patients assigned to a professional.
- Explore details of a patient.
- Explore exercises and routines existing in the system.
- Explore exercises and routines assigned to a patient.
- Sort exercises by name and module.
- Create exercises and routines.
- Assign exercises and routines to a patient.
- Delete exercises and routines.
- Delete exercises and routines assigned to a patient.
- Identify the location of the facility to which they belong.
- Edit his/her user details.
- Go to the system start.
- Close session.

Once the task has been performed, it could be observed from Table 4 that there were some barriers in the application components. 60% of healthcare professionals experienced problems with the top navigation tabs in tasks such as searching for information on an assigned patient, viewing patient routines and exercises, or even not finding the exact functionality of this component. All of these factors complicated the completion of tasks and the navigation within the application. Consequently, 50% had problems with navigation and, more importantly, they found it difficult to understand which profile they were in when they were performing the task. On the other hand, the links provided for ordering exercises and routines were perceived as barriers by 40 percent of users. Tips that were intended to assist users in completing tasks went unnoticed, as 50% did not take them into account. The other evaluated components were not perceived as a barrier, although 20% did not find the use of the drop-down menu useful and were also confused with some of the options displayed in the exercise and routine forms.

Table 4: ICF-US II Results

	Barrier	Facilitator	Average [-3,3]
Components of the application			
Authentication	0%	100%	2.2
Search Bar	0%	100%	1.7
Dropdown menu	20%	80%	1.2
Top navigation tabs	60%	40%	-0.9
Bottom navigation tabs	0%	100%	1.4
Buttons	0%	100%	1.9
Links	40%	60%	0.5
Forms	20%	80%	1.6
Tips	50%	50%	0.2
Edit form	0%	100%	1.8
Location bar	10%	90%	0.8
Navigation	50%	50%	0.1
Detailed Usability			
Image size	40%	60%	0.2
Image color	10%	90%	1.1
Image contrast	0%	100%	1.3
Icons size	40%	60%	0.3
Icons color	0%	100%	1.3
Icons contrast	0%	100%	1.3
Icons intrinsic meaning	0%	100%	1.1
Text size	60%	100%	-0.5
Text font	20%	100%	0.6
Text color	0%	100%	1.3
Overall system evaluation			
Session flow	10%	90%	1

Regarding the detailed usability, the biggest barrier encountered by healthcare professionals is the size of the text (60%), especially in links and tips. Furthermore, they considered the text employed for the editing of repetitions and exercise time to be small. For this reason, they also perceived the size of some images (40%) and icons (40%) as a barrier. On the other hand, the used colours and contrast were evaluated positively.

Overall, the evaluation of the application was positive as all users who underwent the test, except for one, were able to understand and perform the tasks they were proposed, although some of them encountered barriers. One user experienced more difficulties, as he found it very difficult to complete certain tasks due to his low level of technology use.

3.5. Use case 4: Wearable Motion Monitoring Devices

Regarding the assessment of physical activity monitoring particularly during physical rehabilitation periods, a prototype was deployed at SAL, the El Salvador nursing home in Pedroche (Spain), to collect and analyse data from the Mi Band 4 smart bands worn by six of its residents for a period of approximately five weeks.

The information collected, as mentioned in Section 2.3.3, comprises: the number of steps, the heart rate, the date and time at which the above data was collected and the MAC address corresponding to each smart band, which will be used to identify the band, therefore preserving the identity of the person wearing it. Furthermore, it was also registered whether or not participants used any type of walking assistance. In this sense, two people can walk without any assistance (MAC addresses F4:74:0C:8B:8D:1F and DD:30:53:74:F9:1D), two people walk with the assistance of a walker (CA:B7:C3:C7:97:42 and CF:16:DA:26:FC:D1), one with crutches (CB:4B:4F:61:37:91) and one with a cane (C6:B9:F6:F9:C7:51), which is hold with the same arm that wears the smart band.

Figure 30 shows the boxplots obtained from the heart rate data series recorded for each participant during the preliminary piloting tests with a duration of roughly 5 weeks. These quantitative data will be recorded and analyzed in particular during the physical rehabilitation sessions to monitor the evolution of the participants. It should be noted, that the heart rate is an important indicator of general health and physical condition.

Figure 30. Boxplots of the heart rate registered by the writbands corresponding to the six participants during the preliminary piloting test

On the other hand, Figure 31 displays the cumulative sum of steps recorded by the smart bands during the preliminary piloting tests. The figure clearly illustrates the level of activity and its trend over a period of time. This quantitative variable will be of great interest to monitor the level of activity during the physical rehabilitation periods.

Figure 31. Acumulted steps registered by the wristbands corresponding to the six participants during the preliminary piloting test

After an initial rough analysis of the data, we discovered that the Mi Band 4 is incorrectly calculating the number of steps when using a walking aid. This smart band relates the swinging movement of the arms when walking with the steps walked by a person. Therefore, when the arm holds a cane, for example, it makes it difficult to count the person's steps and the resulting information is inaccurate. To overcome such limitation, the accuracy and effectiveness of the Mi Band 4 smart band placed in other parts of the body, such as the ankle, is being studied, as well as the use of other devices with better performance in terms of step counting.

4. Conclusions

This work presents a smart-mirror based platform, designed fit-for-purpose to support independent living for older adults with neurodegenerative diseases and to promote at-home physical activity and rehabilitation. To this end, a set of hardware and software elements have been proposed and experimentally validated under the use cases designed for two of the SHAPES pilot themes.

One of the main limitations of technological solutions proposed for older adults is the lack of engagement they find or their reluctance to use technology. The proposed platform has focused on overcoming such barriers by proposing a mirror-inspired device, with which older adults are familiar with, as well as by providing natural interfaces (based on voices and the use of simple RFID band). To this end, both hardware and software systems have gone through a co-design process, therefore ensuring that requirements were well understood and catered for.

Despite the fact that the smart mirror concept is not new, its application to the healthy and active ageing paradigm, and more specifically to the two purposes of this work (independent living and at-home physical activity) is novel and disruptive. It is also novel the way how the platform enables a privacy-aware solution, ensuring that data are always under the control of the SHAPES platform. This aspect is achieved, maintaining the functionality levels and cost already achieved by commercial products. It would be totally unfeasible to achieve such functionality levels, aesthetic design and prices, working with non-commercial products. Efforts have therefore been addressed to

ensure privacy and data ownership while adopting commercial products (e.g., Mi Band 4, IKEA or Lidl sensors).

The experimental validation of the obtained system have demonstrated the success in meeting the non-functional requirements (privacy, data ownership, performance and accuracy). It has also demonstrated that functional requirements were met, by deploying a real setup and running under different use cases. This has, however, bring into light several limitations of the proposed solutions. The Mi Band 4 smart band performs poorly when the user is using a walking aid. Also, the Phyx.io system has some barriers with regard to the interface design that will be addressed in the following versions.

Finally, as future work, once that the SHAPES smart mirror platform has been validated, the impact of the different interventions it supports will have to be measured. This will be done during the final phase of SHAPES pilots, consisting in the deployment in real-life use cases.

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